

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10809698>

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ABOUT THE CITY OF LARSA

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ABSTRACT

This article is about the centuries-old city of Larsa, which is located in Mesopotamia and includes the years 1822-1763 BC. An attempt is made to provide general information about this city based on the analysis of sources.

Keywords: *Babylon, Mesopotamia, Amorites, Nippur, Lagash, Ur, Sumer, Isin, Hammurabi, Eshnunna, Mari, Ashur.*

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada ko'p asrlik tarixga ega Larsa shahri haqida bo'lib, bu shahar Mesopotamiyada joylashgan, miloddan avvalgi 1822-1763-yillarni o'z ichiga oladi. Bu shahar haqida manbvalar tahlili asosida umumiy ma'lumotlar berishga harakat qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: *Babil, Mesopotamiya, Amoritlar, Nippur, Lagash, Ur, SHumer, Isin, Xammurapi, Eshnunna, Mari, Ashshur.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье речь идет о многовековом городе Ларса, который расположен в Месопотамии и охватывает 1822-1763 годы до нашей эры. Сделана попытка дать общие сведения об этом городе на основе анализа источников.

Ключевые слова: *Вавилон, Месопотамия, Амореи, Ниппур, Лагаш, Ур, Шумер, Исин, Хаммурапи, Эшнунна, Мари, Ашур.*

INTRODUCTION. According to the information given about this city, we can see that it was one of the cities located in Babylon, that is, in Mesopotamia. Mil. avv. At the beginning of the 19th century, Larsa and its rival Isin survived the invasions of the nomadic western Semitic and Amorite tribes. These two cities survived the invasion, and Larsa achieved political and economic prosperity in a short time during the Amorite period. However, it is also mentioned in some information that it was the center of Sumerian culture during this period. The priests of Nippur even wrote a hymn in honor of their ruler Nur-adad between 1865 and 1850 BCE, an honor previously reserved only for the ruler and kings Cheers and Isin. This city was offered deals by Hammurabi, but eventually these cities were conquered by the Babylonian ruler Hammurabi. A brick royal palace was built in Larsa, and the irrigation system was significantly improved [6].

In Mesopotamia, special trade agents, tamkars were engaged in trade, and they also engaged in house, garden, land, loans, and usury for their services. A free man with large trade centers such as Babylon, Ur, Larsa, etc. was called avelium (man)[3]. At the same time, Larsa also waged successful wars with Babylon and eventually captured Nippur. He tries hard to spread his influence in the regions along the Tigris. However, from the sources that have reached us, it is possible to conclude that the first branches of Larsa did not have much influence outside their cities and probably recognized the authority of Isin kings over them. Around 1924 BC, the rise of the city of Larsa was observed. After Sumer and Gungunum ascended the throne, he received the title of "King of Akkad", and his power extended to the cities of Lagash and Ur. The Amorites ruled in 1898 BC under the rule of Gungunum, the son of Abisarikh. King Isin inflicts a serious defeat on Ur-Ninurata, but Larsa's reign in Mesopotamia did not last long. Around 50AD, during the reign of King Nur-Adad, his kings lost control over the cities of Uruk. The dynasty of Nur-Adad began to rule here. During the time of Nur-Adad's successors, the city of Sumer was a holy city for the Amorites. Gudurmabug, one of the leaders of the Amorite Yamutbals tribe, takes power in Larsa,

but he does not accept the royal title and continues to live outside the city walls. BC Around 1826, King Gudurmabug managed to recover the holy city of Nippur from Isin. Soon after, he proclaims his son, young Varad-Sin, as the new king of Larsa. However, Rim-Sin, the second only son of the royal throne, will take the throne. Under his rule, Larsa experienced its last period of growth and dominance. In the 1830s BC, the rise of the Babylonian kingdom and the sharp increase in wars with neighboring city-states caused the decline of Larsa. After the decline of the city of Larsa, in 1794-1792 BC, Rim-Sin I also conquered its main rival, the kingdom of Isin. During the reign of Rim-Sin I, BC. In 1763, Larsa entered the period of growth again. It became the largest city in Lower Mesopotamia. The prosperity of the Babylonian state, the sixth king of the dynasty Hammurabi BC. (1792-1750) period. BC At the end of the 19th century, the Amorite ruler Shamshi-Add (1824-1870) took over the country. BC Around 1800, Shamshi-Add subjugates southern Mesopotamia, the center of the kingdom of Larsa, the city of Babylon, Eshnunna, in Upper Mesopotamia, the kingdom of Mari. We can know that the distance between the ruins of big cities like Larsa and Uruk is only 24 km, and the population lived very peacefully. The vast meadows and steppes to the west of the Frot had the opportunity to engage in animal husbandry [1]. One of the important directions of Hammurabi's political activity was to gain control over the distribution of the waters of the Euphrates. Such a policy is inconveniently located downstream of the Froats. It led to a conflict with the kingdom of Larsa, in the year of Hammurabi's accession to the throne, Rim-Sin, the ruler of Larsa, won Isi, the shepherd, who acted as a buffer between Babylon in the north and Larsa in the south. Then, for 20 years, there were no direct military conflicts between Mari, Asshur, Eshnunna, Larsa, Babylon, which were considered important kingdoms of Mesopotamia, but Hammurabi made a secret alliance to attract allies, control the borders gave great importance to strengthening works. On the basis of this information, where the location of the city and its territory are given correctly, it can be said that the sources from which this information was found are one of the important kingdoms of Mesopotamia in the 20 years above. In 1763 BC, Hammurabi started the long-planned

military operations against Larsa. This followed a tactic his father had used at the same time, Hammurabi damming the main canal that supplied Larsa with water. Then the dam burst open and flooded the city. During the reign of Isin-Larsa, the great ruler of Babylon, the city became a political power. After the fall of the Third Dynasty of Ur. In 2000 BC, Ishbi-Erra, the eunuch of Ibbi-Sin, the last king of the Third Dynasty of Ur, moved to Isin. Established a government believed to be the successor to the Third Dynasty of Ur. From there Ishbi-Erra took back the urn, as well as the cities of Uruk and Lagash, which were subject to Larsa. Later rulers of Isin appointed governors to rule over Larsa, one of the governors was an Amorite named Gungunum. He eventually broke with Isin and established an independent dynasty in Larsa. To legitimize his rule and strike back at Isin, Gungunum captured the city of Ur. As the Larsa region was the main center of trade through the Persian Gulf, Isin lost a very useful trade route and a city of great cultural importance.

Gungunum's two successors, Abisare 1841-1830 BC and Samuel 1830-1801 BC, both took steps to completely cut off access to Isin. Walter Andrae, who also worked briefly in Larsa in 1903. The site was surveyed by Edgar James Banks in 1905. He found that there was widespread looting by the locals. British geologist V. Loftus also made great contributions to the excavation and scientific study of ancient cities in Mesopotamia. He made great discoveries in Uruk and Larsa. In the second half of the 19th century, the British expedition conducted excavations in Sumerian cities such as Uruk and Larsa [2].

The first modern, scientific, excavation of Senkereh took place in 1933, and André Parrott worked at the site again in 1967. Larsa was excavated by Jean-Claude Margueron in 1969-1970. Between 1976 and 1991 there was an expedition. If I give information about the above city of Larsa, this city is considered one of the ancient cities. This city also has its own history and literature, for example, many foreign scientists have studied this city, as well as scientists from our own country. Information about the conquest by Hammurabi, and the cities Larsa had contact with and cooperated with, and with which it fought and fought. In order for this information to reach us, in

1903 Walter Andre also briefly worked on the city of Larsa, and in 1905 it was investigated by Edgar James Banks. I will not be mistaken if I say that this information has reached us based on the research and research of these scientists and many others. This is my opinion about archeological excavations, I mean that archaeologists use planigraphic, stratigraphic, and excavation methods to find any ancient building or monument. The stratigraphic excavation method is defined as 3-3, 4-4, and excavating the excavation area. It should also be said that the city of Isin, which always competes with the city of Larsa. Er. Avv. The material cultural monuments of the III-I millennia were discovered as a result of the excavation of the ruins of the ancient cities of Mesopotamia, Eredu, Uruk, Lagash, Nippur, Eshnunna, Mari, Assur, Nineveh and Babylon. Through the study of these cities, a lot of information learned by scholars has reached us, and at the same time, by reading this information, we can learn the history of this city and also the history of Babylon. is serving as information.

In the study of the economy of the oldest Mesopotamia, the documents related to economic reports found in the archives of Larsa, Umma, Ur, Lagash and other cities in ancient Sumer are of great importance. These reports include extensive collections of labor reports, slave trade contracts, merchants' income and expenses, and price lists. BC The 14th-12th centuries provide rich material for the description of the remains of the community system and the study of farming forms. There are administrative correspondences of the Babylonian king Hammurabi with other city officials, especially with the officials and nobles of Larsa city. In addition, it allows us to imagine the artificial irrigation and administrative management method of Babylon in the first half of the second millennium BC. Many lease agreements and documents have been found and studied in our possession to describe the various land lease ordinances of that time. 2 The conquering Amorites established several states. Two of them turned out to be very powerful and they were called Sumerian and Akkadian kings, that is, they claimed to rule over the whole country. These countries were Isin and Larsa. However, as they weakened each other, they did not have the strength to implement their claims. Moreover, Larsa was under the strong influence of neighboring Elam. Its

kings put their people on the throne of this city-state. The kingdoms of the Amorites actually played an independent role except between the two rivers [5].

Having thus secured the peace of his northern frontier, Hammurabi turned against Larsa, which was connected with Elam. Indications in the documents that make it possible to determine whether different events took place at the same time or whether different political figures lived at the same time help to determine the chronology. For example, the documents found in Eshnunna and Mari allow us to determine that Eshnunna king Ibalpin, Mari king Zimrilim, Babylonian king Hamurapi, Larsa king Rimsin and Assyrian king Shamshidat I were contemporaries. Along with this, Uruk and Larsa are located on the banks of the river Frot. Today, the ruins of these cities are located east of the Euphrates River [2]. Governor Lugal-zagissi established the Sumerian kingdom by subjugating the city-states of Ur, Uruk and Larsa.

In conclusion, this city is located in Mesopotamia, and the history of its development and conquest is very interesting. The rise of Larsa and its place in trade and the neighboring cities of Larsa, Nippur, Eshnunna, Mari, Nineveh, Asshur, Lagash, are examples of these cities. The history of this city has been studied for a long time, the names of many scientists who studied the city of Larsa are written above, which makes people very happy. Because it creates a great opportunity for us to study the history of the Ancient World.

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